

A Study on the Conductimetric Determination of Ion-association Constants and Walden Product for some Transition Metal Sulphates in Aqueous Urea Solutions

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Ion-association constants for dilute solutions of nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) sulphates in urea-water mixtures (11.52, 30.31, 29.64 and 36.83 urea wt%) were determined by means of conductivity measurements between 298 and 313 K. The Walden product has been calculated for all the three electrolytes in different compositions of urea-water at 303 K. The temperature effect on Walden product in 11.52% urea-water mixture shows that all the three electrolytes behave as structure-makers/promoters.

Although studies on electrical conductance in binary systems are abundant, those on ternary systems are few. Moreover, physicochemical studies on ternary systems in aqueous solutions are gaining importance because it is sometimes difficult to arrive at a definite conclusion regarding structure and properties of solutions from the studies on binary systems alone.

A survey of literature showed that data on 2 : 2 electrolytes, particularly transition metal sulphates, in aqueous non-electrolyte systems are non-existent. Since the structure of urea-water mixtures is of great importance in understanding protein denaturation^{1,2} in urea + water mix-

tures, the title investigation has been carried out with a view to determine (i) equivalent conductance at infinite dilution, (ii) ion-association constants, (iii) Walden product and to investigate the structure-making/breaking capacity of transition metal sulphates from the temperature effect of Walden product.

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductivities (Λ_c) for nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) sulphates in aqueous urea solutions (11.52, 20.31, 29.64 and 36.83 wt% urea) at 303 K are summarised in Table 1. The limiting equivalent conduc-

TABLE 1—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTIVITIES (Λ_c) OF NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND ZINC(II) SULPHATES IN DIFFERENT UREA-WATER SOLUTIONS AT 303 K

Nickel sulphate		Copper sulphate		Zinc sulphate	
$10^2 c$ g eq dm ³	Λ_c $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ eq}^{-1}$	$10^2 c$ g eq dm ³	Λ_c $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ eq}^{-1}$	$10^2 c$ g eq dm ³	Λ_c $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ eq}^{-1}$
11.52 (% by wt) urea-water					
0.204	159.88	0.206	131.88	0.204	130.86
0.614	116.00	0.616	109.31	0.614	112.51
1.022	100.37	1.025	98.25	1.022	98.61
1.431	92.45	1.436	92.00	1.430	91.98
2.043	83.80	2.050	85.00	2.044	84.15
6.138	64.40	6.137	55.58	6.116	63.61
10.176	54.70	10.208	49.73	10.170	54.37
14.226	48.49	14.262	44.65	14.204	50.11
20.258	42.52	20.314	38.82	20.222	44.60
20.31 (% by wt) urea-water					
0.210	157.00	0.210	144.77	0.210	149.86
0.630	109.65	0.629	100.89	0.630	105.78
1.048	92.88	1.049	91.15	1.048	93.37
2.096	80.56	1.468	84.61	1.468	87.81
6.271	59.82	2.098	77.13	2.096	79.56
10.427	51.53	6.276	58.65	6.271	60.36
14.556	45.78	10.442	46.61	10.424	52.04
20.718	40.67	14.590	44.12	14.554	44.10
		20.780	38.70	20.704	40.61
29.64 (% by wt) urea-water					
0.214	143.63	0.215	139.35	0.214	148.44
0.645	101.45	0.645	94.09	0.644	101.58
1.074	89.66	1.075	87.29	1.074	88.20
1.504	82.47	1.505	79.39	1.504	72.64
2.148	75.69	2.149	73.61	2.147	62.64

29.64 (% by wt) urea-water				Table 1 (Contd.)	
6.428	57.53	6.429	52.37	6.424	54.09
10.690	48.48	10.701	44.43	10.678	47.87
14.928	46.27	14.950	39.21	14.906	43.77
21.246	39.49	21.285	33.78	21.204	38.83
36.83 (% by wt) urea-water					
0.218	135.39	0.219	136.05	0.220	143.20
0.656	92.54	0.657	87.09	0.656	96.53
1.094	84.82	1.095	76.66	1.094	82.76
1.532	78.23	1.533	71.04	1.532	76.06
2.186	72.30	2.188	67.06	2.188	69.28
6.540	51.75	6.548	56.48	6.544	49.50
10.868	47.03	10.893	46.28	10.878	42.40
15.160	44.65	15.217	39.23	15.184	41.01
21.564	38.18	21.667	34.62	21.596	34.33

tivity (A_0) and the ion-association constants (K_A) for the equilibrium,

were calculated from the conductivity data on the basis of Fuoss-Kraus equation³. The Fuoss-Kraus method³ consists of plotting (F/A_c) versus ($C A_c f_{\pm}^2/F$) according to the function,

$$\frac{F}{A_c} = \frac{1}{A_0} + \frac{C A_c f_{\pm}^2}{F} \left(K_A / A_0^2 \right) \quad (1)$$

where, $F = 4/3 \cos^2 [1/3 \cos^{-1} (-3^{3/2} Z/2)]$, $f_{\pm}^2$ is the limiting Debye-Hückel function for the activity coefficients, and $Z = (S/A_0^{3/2}) (C A_c)^{1/2}$. Values of the function F have been tabulated⁴ for useful ranges of the variable Z . In our case, a computer programme has been used and the values of A_0 and K_A thus calculated are recorded in Table 2.

The values of Walden product obtained from Fuoss-Kraus method are given in Table 3 and it is evident that the Walden product has positive value for all the three electrolytes and increases with increase of urea composition at 303 K.

Further, the Fuoss equation⁵,

$$K_A = \frac{4 \pi N a^3}{3000} \exp \left(|Z_1 Z_2| e^2 / a D k T \right) \quad (2)$$

gives the effect of dielectric constant (D) of the medium on the ion-pair association constant (K_A) of an electrolyte. In the present case, the plot of $\ln K_A$ against $1/D$, is non-linear for all the three electrolytes indicating the presence of specific ion-solvent interactions or the presence of preferential solvation of the ions by aqueous urea. This type of non-linearity was also reported by Conti *et al.*^{6,7} which was attributed to the existence of strong interactions between the solvent and the anion of the electrolyte. Hynes⁸ also studied the conductance of Bu_4NBr in water + dioxane mixtures. The plot of $\ln K_A$ versus $1/D$ for Bu_4NBr deviated strongly from linearity indicating specific ion-solvent interactions.

Effect of temperature : Since the behaviour of all the electrolytes in different compositions of urea-water was

TABLE 2—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE (A_0) AND ION-ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (K_A) FOR NICKEL (II), COPPER (II) AND ZINC (II) SULPHATES IN AQUEOUS UREA SOLUTION AT 303 K

Urea-water (% by wt)	A_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ eq}^{-1}$	K_A mol ⁻¹
Nickel sulphate		
11.52	190.85	113.90
20.31	184.17	132.81
29.64	168.60	116.87
36.83	151.47	90.26
Copper sulphate		
11.52	142.41	(a)
20.31	162.15	72.77
29.64	155.08	85.04
36.83	153.46	141.00
Zinc sulphate		
11.52	146.26	15.67
20.31	170.85	86.98
29.64	189.69	222.37
36.83	183.53	241.39

(a) $K_A < 10$ have no physical significance (Ref. 13) and therefore not reported.

TABLE 3—DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D) AND THE WALDEN PRODUCT ($A_0 \eta_0$) OF NICKEL (II), COPPER (II) AND ZINC (II) SULPHATES IN DIFFERENT AQUEOUS UREA SOLUTIONS AT 303 K

Parameter	Urea (wt %)			
	11.52	20.31	29.64	36.83
D^a	82.03	86.04	89.83	92.48
$10^3 \eta_0(P)^b$	8.73	9.51	10.64	11.82
Nickel sulphate				
$A_0 \eta_0$	1.67	1.75	1.79	1.79
Copper sulphate				
$A_0 \eta_0$	1.24	1.54	1.65	1.81
Zinc sulphate				
$A_0 \eta_0$	1.27	1.62	2.02	2.17

^a Values taken from Ref. 14. ^b Determined as described in Ref. 11.

found to be identical at 303 K, only 11.52% urea-water composition was selected for studying the effect of temperature. The values of equivalent conductivity (A_c) for nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) sulphates in 11.52% urea-water at different temperatures (298, 308 and 313 K) are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTIVITIES (Λ_c) OF NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND ZINC(II) SULPHATE IN 11.52 (WT %) UREA-WATER MIXTURE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

298 K		308 K		313 K	
$10^2 c$ g eq dm ⁻³	Λ_c $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{eq}^{-1}$	$10^2 c$ g eq dm ⁻³	Λ_c $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{eq}^{-1}$	$10^2 c$ g eq dm ⁻³	Λ_c $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{eq}^{-1}$
Nickel sulphate					
0.205	128.20	0.204	175.22	0.204	190.33
0.608	110.34	0.608	134.28	0.615	145.32
1.022	94.17	1.022	101.94	1.024	108.60
1.430	88.18	1.431	100.07	1.438	104.62
2.053	80.12	2.043	86.00	2.048	90.24
6.146	62.16	6.104	68.69	6.107	72.64
10.219	54.29	10.156	58.29	10.151	63.68
Copper sulphate					
0.205	109.13	0.205	142.32	0.205	160.08
0.615	98.21	0.618	112.32	0.618	123.36
1.022	90.00	1.022	99.08	1.028	106.74
1.431	83.27	1.428	91.15	1.430	96.64
2.048	72.24	2.044	81.23	2.048	85.33
6.148	48.15	6.124	66.94	6.120	74.68
10.227	44.63	10.186	57.88	10.178	64.10
Zinc sulphate					
0.205	102.79	0.205	161.21	0.205	201.89
0.614	99.49	0.614	120.32	0.614	125.47
1.022	92.36	1.024	104.74	1.022	110.83
1.428	86.86	1.438	96.37	1.432	103.22
2.044	79.19	2.044	90.32	2.044	96.37
6.145	61.03	6.119	69.84	6.114	76.46
10.271	53.61	10.171	61.23	10.162	66.09

The values of the limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) and the ion-association constant (K_A), obtained by Fuoss-Kraus method, are recorded in Table 5. The values of the Walden product ($\Lambda_0 \eta_0$) of nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) sulphates in 11.52% urea at different temperatures are recorded in Table 6. The positive temperature coefficient of the Walden product can be attributed to the structure-making/promoting^{9,10} characteristic of all the three electrolytes. These conclusions from conductivity measurements are in excellent agreement with those drawn from viscometric and volumetric properties¹¹ of these electrolytes in aqueous

urea. The structure-making characteristic may be attributed to the solvation of the ions. The order of solvation in 11.52% urea-water is : NiSO₄ > ZnSO₄ > CuSO₄. Since SO₄²⁻ ion is common in all the electrolytes, the solvation order for different cations in 11.52% urea-water may be expressed as : Ni²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Cu²⁺.

TABLE 5—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE (Λ_0 , $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{eq}^{-1}$) AND ION-ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (K_A) FOR NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND ZINC(II) SULPHATES IN 11.52 (WT %) UREA-WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Parameter	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
Nickel sulphate				
Λ_0	148.34	190.85	236.21	298.65
K_A	13.19	113.90	232.83	—
Copper sulphate				
Λ_0	120.92	142.41	160.28	195.62
K_A	(a)	—	—	80.56
Zinc sulphate				
Λ_0	113.25	146.26	175.91	218.41
K_A	—	86.98	19.24	107.23

(a) $K_A < 10$ have no physical significance (Ref. 13) and therefore, not reported

TABLE 6—DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D) AND WALDEN PRODUCT ($\Lambda_0 \eta_0$) FOR NICKEL(II), COPPER(II) AND ZINC(II) SULPHATES IN 11.52% UREA-WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Parameter	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
D^a	83.90	82.03	80.21	78.43
$10^3 \eta_0$ (P) ^b	9.82	8.73	7.91	6.90
Nickel sulphate				
$\Lambda_0 \eta_0$	1.46	1.67	1.87	2.06
Copper sulphate				
$\Lambda_0 \eta_0$	1.18	1.24	1.27	1.35
Zinc sulphate				
$\Lambda_0 \eta_0$	1.11	1.28	1.39	1.54

^a Values taken from Ref. 14. ^b Determined as described in Ref. 11.

Experimental

Nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) sulphates and urea (all AnalaR) were used as such after drying over P₂O₅. Fresh distilled conductivity water (sp. cond. $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) was used for preparing the urea-water mixtures. The urea-water mixtures of varying compositions (density accuracy $\pm 0.0001 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) and the solutions of electrolytes were made by weight (accuracy $\pm 0.001 \text{ g}$), and molalities were con-

verted into molarities using the standard expression described elsewhere¹². The conductivity measurement was carried out with the help of a Naina NDC 732 conductivity meter at 50 Hz. The runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within $\pm 0.0001 \Omega^{-1}$. The conductivity cell (cell constant $0.1745 \pm 0.0001 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used. All measurements were carried out in a water-bath ($\pm 0.01^\circ$).

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